

A mass fruiting of *Physarum confertum* in West Virginia

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Abstract: During June and early July of 2000, a mass fruiting of *Physarum confertum* occurred on the Fernow Experimental Forest and adjacent areas of the Allegheny Mountains of West Virginia. At some localities, it was estimated that there >10 fruitings per 100 m². Many of the fruitings were quite large, sometimes exceeding 10 to 15 cm in total extent. In almost 25 years of collecting throughout West Virginia at the time, the first co-author had not previously encountered this species. Just what factor triggered the mass fruiting is unknown, but the occurrence of fruitings of the same species of myxomycete in a particular locality is not an uncommon phenomenon.

Keywords: ecology, Fernow Experimental Forest, myxomycetes, slime molds

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Introduction

Numerous studies of myxomycetes (also called myxogastrids) have been carried out worldwide. Much is now known about their taxonomy, biology, ecology, and distribution. However, our knowledge of this group of organisms is not yet complete, and sometimes myxomycetes display unusual patterns of occurrence. The objective of this paper is to describe one particularly noteworthy example.

Observations in the field

During the June and July of 2000, the first coauthor carried out project that involved obtaining data on the structure and composition of upland forest communities on the USDA Fernow Experimental Forest (39°03'E, 79°40'W) in the Allegheny Mountains of eastern central West Virginia. He was assisted by the second coauthor, who was then working in the former's laboratory as a post-doc. These forests of the Fernow are dominated by various broadleaf trees, with species of oak (*Quercus* spp.) the most important. During fieldwork carried out on June 8, it was noticed that the fruitings of an initially unidentified myxomycete were consciously present on forest floor litter throughout the forest community (elevation 704 m) in which fieldwork was being carried out (Fig. 1). In some areas of the forest floor, there were >10

fruitings per 100 m². On subsequent visits to the Fernow on June 26, July 1, and July 2, the same phenomenon was observed in three other upland forest communities. Two of these were oak-dominated communities similar to one mentioned above, but the third was a coniferous forest community (38°36'N, 79°50'W) dominated by red spruce (*Picea rubra* Sarg.) and located at a much higher elevation (1224 m) and 30 km away. The fruitings of what had now been identified *Physarum confertum* T.Macbr. were observed in the coniferous forests usually occurred in association with bryophytes (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Fruiting of *Physarum confertum* on forest floor litter.

Figure 2. Fruiting of *Physarum confertum* on bryophytes.

Representative specimens of *Physarum confertum* collected during this mass fruiting in 2000 are Stephenson 13149, 17407, 17486, 17487 and 17575; Schnittler 29428, 29431 and 29495. These were initially deposited in the herbarium of the University of Arkansas (UARK) but later transferred to the herbarium of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IB PAN).

Discussion

In his original description of *P. confertum*, Thomas Macbride (1922) indicated that this species produces small (0.2 to 0.4 mm in diam.) sporocarps that are closely gregarious and often confluent or heaped. Little lime is present, and the sporocarps appear to be nearly black in color. Neither Macbride or Martin and Alexopoulos (1969) commented on the typical size of fruitings, but many of the examples observed in the present study were quite large, sometimes exceeding 10 to 15 cm in total extent.

Interestingly, the first author, who had been collecting and studying myxomycetes in West Virginia for almost twenty-five years in 2000, had never previously encountered this species in the state. Moreover, specimens of *P. confertum* listed in MycoPortal (2024) for the United States did not list any records of specimens collected in West Virginia. When the data in MycoPortal were checked, there were 135 records of *P. confertum* from the United States, nine of which had no locality data. The species appears to be relatively common in the northern United States and rare in the western United States. Although there were no records listed for West Virginia, records did exist for all of the surrounding states (Virginia, Ohio, Pennsylvania, and Maryland) except for Kentucky.

Anyone who has collected myxomycetes in the field has undoubtedly noticed that multiple fruitings of a particular species are commonly found in the same locality on a collecting trip or foray. Usually, the species involved tend to be common and widespread. Presumably, the fruiting response is triggered by some environmental factor or combination of factors. However, what makes the mass fruiting of *P. confertum* unusual is that it involved an apparently uncommon species and the fruitings occurred over an area of many hundreds of square kilometers.

References

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